

MANOEUVRE

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REPowerEU

Man0EUvRE – Case Study 2: Stochastic modelling of the Nordic power system

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

Table 1: List of acronyms and abbreviations

Term	Explanation
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CETP	Clean Energy Transition Partnership
DMP	Data Management Plan
ECEMF	European Climate and Energy Modelling Forum
EERA	European Energy Research Alliance

EU	European Union
IEA-ETSAP	International Energy Agency - Energy Technology Systems Analysis Program
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
REPowerEU	European Commission plan to phase out Russian fossil fuel imports
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This report presents a Norwegian case study within the Man0EUvRE project that uses data from the long-term European energy system capacity expansion model GENeSYS-MOD as input to the detailed stochastic power market model FanSi. The FanSi analysis focuses on the year 2050 under the EU EnVis-2060 energy transition scenario called NECP Essentials and investigates how different forms of flexibility expansions in Norway influence power system operation in Northern Europe.

Using the NECP Essentials 2050 scenario results from GENeSYS-MOD as a baseline framework, the study evaluates four stylized flexibility expansion scenarios: enhanced hydropower flexibility (+HydroFlex), price-responsive demand (+ElasticDemand), time-shiftable demand (+TimeShiftDemand), and increased cross-border transmission capacity (+TransFlex). These scenarios are not forecasts but are designed to explore the relative system impacts of different flexibility mechanisms. Each flexibility scenario is evaluated against the NECP Essentials base case to isolate its systemic effects for Norway.

Under the baseline framework, average electricity prices in Norway are considerably lower than in continental Europe and the United Kingdom. The lower Norwegian prices reflect a substantial electricity surplus for Norway combined with limited cross-border export capacity in NECP Essentials. Price volatility is also considerably lower in Norway than in continental Europe and the United Kingdom, an effect attributable to the substantial flexibility provided by Norway's hydropower. The differences in price levels and volatility across regions create distributional effects, including lower capture prices for offshore wind in Norway compared to neighbouring markets.

Hydropower plays a central role in balancing variability, particularly by offsetting intraday fluctuations in solar generation. As such, Norwegian hydropower provides valuable flexibility in the European energy system. Cross-border interconnections are frequently used in both directions, reflecting dynamic trade patterns even in a surplus system. There is strong interannual variation in prices as well as other system indicators across individual weather years, underscoring the relevance of multi-year analysis for planning.

The results show that flexibility options target different types of variability. Hydropower flexibility and time-shifting of demand significantly dampen intraday price fluctuations linked to solar generation, while elastic demand provides more moderate but consistent reductions in both short- and medium-term price variability linked to wind power. In contrast, increased transmission capacity (+TransFlex) primarily reduces regional differences in both price levels, price volatility and capture prices for offshore wind power. These mechanisms therefore act in a complementary way, addressing distinct dimensions of variability.

The +TransFlex scenario reduces price differences between Norway and neighbouring markets and increases overall system efficiency. However, it also exposes Norway more directly to higher price volatility from continental Europe, leading to increased price variability domestically. This illustrates that transmission delivers system-level gains, but the benefits can be unevenly shared.

Overall, the study demonstrates that different forms of flexibility have distinct and complementary roles. Hydropower and demand-side measures are most effective for managing temporal variability, while increase in transnational transmission reduces regional differences. A balanced combination of these flexibility options can support the efficient and stable operation of a future European power system with high shares of renewable energy.

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1 Introduction

This report presents a Norwegian case study conducted within the European research project ManOEUVRE, which combines pan-European energy system modelling with the GENeSYS-MOD model [1] and regional case studies that use separate models with enhanced regional details. The present analysis is based on year-2050 GENeSYS-MOD results for the scenario NECP Essentials [2], which reflects National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) to 2040 and a continuation of trends thereafter.

We use the stochastic power market model FanSi, which offers multi-year stochastic optimization and a detailed representation of hydropower in the Nordics [3]. Our approach systematically transfers data on power generation, transmission, storage and electricity demand from GENeSYS-MOD to FanSi. This ensures a coherent dataset of installed capacities and demand for use in FanSi.

The case study has two purposes. First, it provides a complementary re-analysis of a GENeSYS-MOD scenario for Scandinavia using a multi-year stochastic optimisation and a more detailed representation of Norwegian hydropower, to generate additional operational insights beyond those available from GENeSYS-MOD alone. Second, it explores stylized expansions of distinct flexibility types in Norway for the year 2050, implemented through scenario variants representing hydropower flexibility (+HydroFlex), elastic demand (+ElasticDemand), time-shiftable demand (+TimeShiftDemand) and transmission expansion (+TransFlex).

The flexibility expansions are not intended as projections of feasible potentials; rather, they examine potential impacts of qualitatively different flexibility types within the Norwegian case study context. The test cases are developed in dialog with Norwegian ManOEUVRE stakeholders and focus on alternative flexibility scenarios due to the considerable build-out of wind power towards 2050 and high shares solar generation in Europe in the NECP Essentials results, which can influence prices in Norway through cross-border interconnections.

The FanSi analysis shows significant differences in both average price levels and price volatility between Norwegian areas and continental Europe and the United Kingdom under the GENeSYS-MOD-based 2050 framework. These differences stem from a substantial net power surplus for Norway and reflect Norway's abundant hydro and wind resources. At the same time, the regional differences or disparities in the FanSi simulations have distributional implications, including for producer revenues, reflected in 26-44% lower offshore wind capture prices in Norway relative to several neighbouring markets. Despite certain modelling choices that tend to dampen extreme price outcomes¹, the FanSi simulations reveal episodes of very high prices in several countries, indicating potential flexibility constraints when the NECP Essentials framework is assessed in a stochastic multi-year operational setting.

With increased demand flexibility the variation in power prices is reduced, which is an expected result, and this work shows is that it gives 50% less variation in the short-term prices when the hydropower capacity is increased but also 17% reduction with better use of demand side flexibility. The weekly or seasonal price variation is not impacted in a similar way and does not change much. +HydroFlex and +TimeShiftDemand and +ElasticDemand are effective at mitigating short-term variability.

In contrast, price variation in Norway increases under +TransFlex because stronger interconnection exposes Norwegian prices more directly to price variation in neighbouring markets. +TransFlex reduces differences between neighbouring countries and enables smarter grids, efficiency (lower prices), and innovative technologies and solutions by supporting the cooperation national power systems which is a goal of European energy policy^{2, 3}.

¹ Stylized curtailment thresholds for demand as discussed in sections 5.3 and 6.2, and remaining coal power capacities, mainly in Germany, in 2050 as discussed in sections 5.1 and 6.2.

² EU Commission, «European Grid Package», COM(2025), 1005, 10-12-2025

³<https://www.entsoe.eu/european-grids-package/>

2 FanSi power market model

We employ the stochastic optimization power market model FanSi [3], which is specifically designed for hydropower-rich systems and applied here to a broad Northern European setting. FanSi has previously been applied in several peer-reviewed studies addressing hydropower flexibility, market outcomes and renewable integration in Northern European power systems [4–9]. The model maximizes expected socioeconomic surplus by optimally dispatching generation and transmission capacity while explicitly representing hydropower reservoir dynamics and other temporal couplings. The current model includes a detailed representation of approximately 1300 individual hydropower modules.

FanSi is formulated as a stochastic optimization model, in which uncertainty in weather conditions is represented using multiple historical weather years. In the current study, uncertainty is represented using thirty historical weather years (1991–2020). The historical weather data encompass hydrological inflow, wind and solar generation and temperature. As a result, the model accounts for uncertain future weather conditions when determining optimal operation.

The use of multiple historical weather years also allows FanSi to analyse system outcomes separately for each weather year. This enables an assessment of how electricity prices, power exchanges between regions, revenues for power producers and costs for consumers vary across different weather years, thereby characterizing the range of outcomes induced by weather variability.

FanSi is particularly well suited for investigating long-duration flexibility: Intraday flexibility to balance day-night variations in solar generation; multi-day to multi-week to manage prolonged periods with low wind and solar generation (“dunkelflaute”); and seasonal flexibility to address longer-term variations in supply and demand.

The stochastic optimization problem is implemented using a rolling-horizon framework with two stages. The first stage is deterministic and solved at high temporal resolution (3-hour intervals in the present study), based on realized weather conditions. The second stage represents uncertainty in future conditions using a coarser temporal resolution (weekly) and historical weather data. The second-stage horizon spans one year, with end-of-horizon water values provided by the EMPS model [10]. A scenario reduction technique is employed in FanSi in this study (as described in ref. [11]) to limit the number of weather years explicitly considered in the second stage to five.

The price areas simulated in FanSi are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 2. Inflow to hydropower in the area NO-SOUTH for the simulated weather years (1991-2020).

Figure 3. Offshore wind power connected to the area NO-SOUTH for the simulated weather years (1991-2020).

3 Scenario basis (NECP Essentials from GENeSYS-MOD)

As the framework for our analyses with FanSi, we use one of the openly available EU EnVis-2060 energy transition scenarios for Europe, namely NECP Essentials, which reflects National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) to 2040 and a continuation of current trends thereafter. Specifically, we use NECP Essentials version 1.0.1 [2], which includes adjustments for Norway and Sweden relative to earlier releases.

The results for NECP Essentials version 1.0.1 are generated by the multi-sector capacity expansion model GENeSYS-MOD [1]. GENeSYS-MOD determines optimal investment pathways in generation, storage, transmission and other infrastructure, and the resulting installed capacities as well as future trajectories for electricity demand are subsequently integrated into FanSi. This ensures coherence between long-term investment pathways and short-term operational analysis. We use results for the year 2050 as input to the FanSi analyses⁴.

⁴ Further details on the data transfer are provided in Section 5.

3.1 Norway’s power balance

Without considering domestic grid energy losses, Norway has an annual net positive power balance of approximately 44 TWh in the GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials results for 2050. This balance results from an annual electricity consumption of 172 TWh and a total annual electricity generation of 216 TWh. By comparison, the most recently available baseline scenario from the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE) shows a total electricity consumption of 190 TWh and electricity production of 205 TWh in 2050 [12].

3.2 Power generation

Figure 4 shows the composition of power generation capacity for selected countries according to the the GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials results for 2050. Figure 5 shows the equivalent results for annual power generation (in TWh year⁻¹) instead of installed capacity. Note that while some coal and gas installed capacities remain in the results reported by GENeSYS-MOD for 2050 (as reflected in Figure 4), these capacities have zero power generation (as reflected in Figure 5).

Figure 4. Power generation capacity (GW) by technology in in year 2050 the GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials scenario used as a basis for FanSi analysis in the current case study. Only the subset of countries from GENeSYS-MOD included in FanSi is shown in this figure. A small amount of oil power capacity is subsumed under the “gas” category. Solar primarily consists of photovoltaic (PV) solar but also a small amount of concentrating solar power (CSP).

Considering annual power generation (Figure 5), the most important source of electricity in Norway is hydropower, with an annual generation of 149 TWh, followed by wind power with 51 TWh, of which 16 TWh is onshore and 35 TWh is offshore. Additional sources of electricity are solar PV (13 TWh) and biomass (2.7 TWh). This compares with figures of 147 TWh hydropower, 33 TWh onshore wind, 17 TWh offshore wind, 10 TWh solar and 1 TWh thermal sources in NVE’s baseline scenario [12].

Figure 5. Annual power generation (TWh) by technology in year 2050 in the GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials scenario used as a basis for FanSi analysis in the current case study. Only the subset of countries from GENeSYS-MOD included in FanSi is shown in this figure. Solar primarily consists of photovoltaic (PV) solar but also a small amount of concentrating solar power (CSP).

Solar power contributes 43% to total power in France, 32% in the Netherlands and 27% in Germany and Denmark. Norway has a smaller relative contribution from solar of 6%. The remainder of the countries obtain 10-25% of their electricity from solar. Onshore wind power represents 39% of the power mix in the United Kingdom and Germany. Offshore wind power is a major contributor to power generation in the Netherlands and Denmark in particular, contributing 52% and 46% of total electricity in the two countries respectively. For Norway, onshore and offshore wind comprise 17% and 7.4%, respectively, of total power generation. Nuclear power is present in the power mix for Sweden, Finland, the Netherlands and France. Biomass-based electricity contributes between 1.2% (for Norway) and 17% (for Denmark) of total electricity for the different countries.

3.3 Battery energy storage

NECP Essentials includes substantial amounts of Li-ion battery energy storage capacities, which constitutes an important source of short-duration flexibility. Table 2 shows the installed battery energy storage system capacity in the countries analysed with the FanSi model. The total across these countries is 164 GW. The battery energy storage duration assumed in NECP Essentials is 3 hours.

Table 2. Battery capacity (in GW) from GENeSYS-MOD for different years in NECP Essentials.

Area/Year	2035	2040	2045	2050
Belgium				1.6
Denmark			0.3	2.2
Finland	1.8	3.4	6.3	8.8
France		2.1	25.4	75.3
Germany			21.1	62.9
Netherlands			1.1	13.9

Norway		1.2	1.3	
Sweden				
United Kingdom	2.8	12.3	30.6	
Sum	1.8	5.5	55.4	164

The battery storage duration of 3 hours implies an energy storage capacity of $164 \text{ GW} \times 3 \text{ hours} = 0.5 \text{ TWh}$ (still referring to the countries listed in Table 2). By comparison, the total hydropower generation capacity in Norway is 34 GW, and the total energy storage capacity of Norway's reservoirs is about 87 TWh [13], corresponding to a theoretical storage duration of more than $87 \text{ TWh} / 34 \text{ GW} = 2000$ hours. This comparison, while highly simplified, illustrates that Norwegian hydropower reservoirs represent a possibility for very large-scale, long-term energy storage. The NECP Essentials scenario results also include pumped storage hydro and compressed air energy storage capacities, but these are relatively small compared to the battery energy storage capacities.

4 Flexibility scenario variants

The starting point for the flexibility scenario variants analysed with FanSi is the NECP Essentials scenario from GENeSYS-MOD as described previously in Section 3. Then, we construct four highly stylized flexibility scenario variants to explore the impacts of expanding four distinct dimensions of system flexibility.

- **Base:** The reference case and the default FanSi implementation the NECP Essentials scenario from GENeSYS-MOD.
- **+HydroFlex:** Add a total of 11 GW generation and 5.2 GW pumping capacity. The added capacities are distributed over twelve locations, of which five are in the area NO-WESTMID, three in NO-WESTSOUTH, three in NO-SOUTH and one in NO-INLAND1.
- **+ElasticDemand:** Introduction of price-responsive demand for 22 TWh load in the areas NO-WESTMID, NO-WESTSOUTH and NO-SOUTH. Demand flexibility is represented through a price elasticity function allowing load to respond to market prices.
- **+TimeShiftDemand:** Add temporal demand-shifting capability for a total of 22 TWh load in total in the areas NO-WESTMID, NO-WESTSOUTH and NO-SOUTH. Demand shifting is represented through energy storage with 9-hour storage duration.
- **+TransFlex:** Add a total of 4.9 GW transmission capacity by doubling the Base transmission capacities between Norway and the United Kingdom, Germany and the Netherlands. The Norwegian areas involved are NO-WESTMID, NO-WESTSOUTH and NO-SOUTH.

Hereafter, the scenario variants listed above are referred to simply as *scenarios*.

With the partial exception of +HydroFlex, the flexibility scenarios are intentionally stylized and do not represent assessments of real-world flexibility potentials. The absolute magnitudes of the implemented flexibility options are not intended to be comparable across scenarios, as there is no consistent empirical basis for calibrating, for example, how much demand elasticity, time-shifting capability or transmission expansion to assume. Rather than enabling absolute comparisons, the purpose of the scenario variants is to explore system impacts associated with distinct types of flexibility and to support relative comparisons across qualitatively different flexibility mechanisms. Another point to note is that the FanSi analyses reflect only operational outcomes and do not consider investment costs associated with flexibility or any other investment costs.

While the geographical scope of FanSi is Northern Europe, the variations in flexibility assumptions across scenarios (see list above) will focus on southern Norway, with emphasis on the areas NO-SOUTH, NO-WESTSOUTH and NO-WESTMID. The scenarios are explained in more detail in the following subsections.

4.1 +HydroFlex

The +HydroFlex scenario represents a targeted expansion of hydropower capacity within the existing Norwegian hydropower system. It includes additions of a total of 11 GW of generation capacity and 5.2 GW of pumping capacity, distributed across twelve locations (five in NO-WESTMID, three in NO-WESTSOUTH, three in NO-SOUTH and one in NO-INLAND1). Inflows and reservoir storage volumes are kept unchanged; the only modifications relative to the baseline are the additions to generation and pumping capacities.

The +HydroFlex scenario is based on the list of applicable hydropower flexibility projects from the CEDREN-HydroBalance project [14] implemented in a FanSi dataset by the previous research project HydroConnect (2021-2024) [9,15,16]. Hydropower expansions must be located where there are hydropower potential and the results from ref. [14] from year 2014 are therefore still relevant. The list of projects is within the current regulation schemes and respect the recommended maximum water level change per hour, 13 cm/hour, as defined by CEDREN. All projects consider existing hydropower reservoirs only and no new reservoirs are added to the hydropower system. The proposed expansions are in this way designed to limit water level variations within acceptable environmental limits.

Table 3. Increases in hydropower generation and pumping capacity included in the +HydroFlex scenario. The added capacities are distributed over twelve locations as previously identified in the CEDREN-HydroBalance project [14] and implemented in FanSi in the HydroConnect project [15,16].

Power plant	Lower reservoir	Upper reservoir	Increased generation (MW)	Increased pumping (MW)	FanSi area
Tonstad	Sirdalsvatn	Nesjen	1400	1400	NO-SOUTH
Holen	Botsvatn	Urarvatn	700	700	NO-SOUTH
Lysebotn	Lysefjorden	Lyngsvatn	1400	-	NO-SOUTH
Tysso	Ringedalsvatn	Langevatn	700	700	NO-WESTSOUTH
Jøsenfjord	Jøsenfjord	Blåsjø	1400	-	NO-WESTSOUTH
Oksla	Hardangerfjord	Ringedalsvatn	700	-	NO-WESTSOUTH
Tinnsjø	Tinnsjø	Møsvatn	1000	1000	NO-INLAND1
Mauranger	Hardangerfjord	Juklavatn	400	-	NO-WESTMID
Sy-Sima	Hardangerfjord	Sysenvatn	700	-	NO-WESTMID
Aurland	Aurlandsfjord	Viddalsvatn	700	-	NO-WESTMID
Tyin	Årdalsvatn	Tyin	700	-	NO-WESTMID
Kvilldal	Suldalsvatn	Blåsjø	1400	1400	NO-WESTMID

Relation of the scenarios to the project HydroConnect (2021-2024) [16]: HydroConnect already analysed power system impacts of implementing all twelve projects included in Table 3 under a future European energy system scenario. The present Man0EUvRE analysis for the +HydroFlex scenario will be distinguished from the HydroConnect analysis by using GENESYS-MOD scenarios as frameworks, which are different from the energy system scenarios used in HydroConnect (e.g., different electricity mixes in Europe).

4.2 +ElasticDemand

In the +ElasticDemand scenario, we expand the scope for demand-side flexibility through load shedding (reductions in electricity consumption during high-price periods) and valley filling (increases in consumption during low-price periods) for the industry sector. The technical implementation in FanSi applies a stylized price elasticity formulation that allows electricity demand to respond endogenously to simulated market prices.

Specifically, demand is reduced when the simulated price exceeds a reference level of 50 EUR MWh⁻¹ and increased when prices fall below this reference level. For instance, a 25% increase in the electricity price results in an 11% reduction in industrial load under this specification. The implemented formulation allows both upward and downward demand adjustments depending on price conditions. This demand flexibility is introduced for a total annual electricity consumption of 22 TWh in the regions NO-WESTMID, NO-WESTSOUTH and NO-SOUTH.

The representation is intentionally simplified and generic. It should be interpreted as an illustration of potential industrial demand flexibility rather than a detailed process-level model of specific technologies or industries.

4.3 +TimeShiftDemand

In the +TimeShiftDemand scenario, we expand the scope for demand-side temporal flexibility through load shifting (reallocation of electricity consumption across time) in the industrial sector. The technical implementation in FanSi represents load shifting using a stylized energy storage formulation that allows electricity demand to be shifted between hours in response to simulated market prices. Specifically, a generic storage technology with a storage duration of 9 hours is introduced, enabling temporal reallocation of electricity consumption while conserving total energy use over time. A round-trip efficiency of 88% is assumed, consistent with the efficiency assumed for 3-hour Li-ion battery storage systems in the analysed system (see Section 5).

The +TimeShiftDemand scenario represents intertemporal substitution of electricity demand, conserving total electricity use while allowing consumption to be shifted across hours⁵. The load shifting capability is introduced for a total annual electricity consumption of 22 TWh in the regions NO-WESTMID, NO-WESTSOUTH and NO-SOUTH, corresponding to the same demand volume as in the +ElasticDemand scenario. The representation is intentionally simplified and stylized; it should be interpreted as an explorative representation of potential industrial load shifting rather than a technology-specific description of individual processes.

4.4 +TransFlex

In the +TransFlex scenario, we expand cross-border transmission capacity to strengthen spatial flexibility in the power system by enhancing the ability to transfer electricity between regions with differing supply-demand balances. The technical implementation in FanSi consists of increasing the available HVDC transmission capacity between Norway and neighbouring power systems.

Specifically, the Base transmission capacities between Norway and the United Kingdom, Germany, and the Netherlands are doubled, corresponding to a total additional transmission capacity of 4.9 GW. The expanded interconnections involve the Norwegian regions NO-WESTMID, NO-WESTSOUTH, and NO-SOUTH. Resulting transmission capacities in the Base and +TransFlex scenarios are summarized in Table 4.

⁵ This is in contrast to the +ElasticDemand scenario, which represents price-responsive demand volumes, allowing total electricity consumption to increase or decrease in response to price signals.

Table 4. Transmission capacities (MW) between southern and mid-Norway and Europe in the Base and +TransFlex scenarios. Two numbers are displayed for NO-SOUTH<->DK-WEST, with first number representing export from NO-SOUTH and second number representing import to NO-SOUTH.

Area in Norway	Other area	Capacities (MW), Base	Capacities (MW), +TransFlex
NO-SOUTH	DK-WEST	2875 / 2743	2875 / 2743
NO-SOUTH	GE-NORTH	1330 / 1330	2660 / 2660
NO-SOUTH	NETHERLANDS	665 / 665	1330 / 1330
NO-SOUTH	SW-MID1	2214 / 2214	2214 / 2214
NO-WESTMID	UK-NORTH	1330 / 1330	2660 / 2660
NO-WESTSOUTH	UK-MID	1330 / 1330	2660 / 2660
NO-MID	SW-MID1	540 / 540	540 / 540

The +TransFlex scenario represents a fundamentally different flexibility mechanism than +HydroFlex, +ElasticDemand and +TimeShiftDemand. Whereas those scenarios increase temporal flexibility within regions – through utilization of reservoir storage capacity and demand-side responses – the +TransFlex scenario increases spatial flexibility by enabling greater power exchange across regions. This allows electricity to be transported more effectively from areas with surplus generation to areas with tighter supply-demand balances.

5 Power system data

5.1 Data transfer: GENeSYS-MOD → FanSi

We systematically transfer the NECP Essentials scenario results from GENeSYS-MOD to FanSi, enabling a coherent representation of the 2050 European energy system and Nordic power system operation. This implementation builds upon and further develop routines and code previously developed in the HydroConnect project [9,15–17] to transfer data from cross-sectoral capacity expansion energy system models into FanSi. The data transfer from GENeSYS-MOD to FanSi includes GENeSYS-MOD variables representing installed generation capacities (onshore wind, offshore wind, solar power, thermal power from bio and gas, and nuclear), demand (industry, buildings, transport and a residual category), transmission capacities, and energy storage (pumped storage hydropower, Li-ion battery storage systems).

The countries Norway, Sweden, Denmark, United Kingdom and Germany are divided into multiple price areas in FanSi, allowing for the representation of geographical variabilities in renewable energy inflow and internal transmission constraints within countries. To disaggregate country-level results from GENeSYS-MOD into subnational areas defined in FanSi, assumed distribution keys for different variables are applied. An example of distribution keys is presented in Table 5 (for onshore wind). Other variables from GENeSYS-MOD are handled in a similar way in their adaptation to the more detailed geographical representation in the FanSi model.

Table 5. Distribution factors for onshore wind. For each country, the relative shares sum to one.

Node	Area name	Relative share	Node	Area name	Relative share
1	NO-EAST	0.1	17	SW-SOUTH	0.17
2	NO-SEAST	0.1	18	GE-EAST	0.14
3	NO-SOUTH	0.1	19	GE-NORTH	0.09
4	NO-WSOUTH	0.1	20	GE-MID	0.14
5	NO-INLAND1	0.05	21	GE-MIDWEST	0.00

6	NO-INLAND2	0.05	22	GE-WEST	0.37
7	NO-WESTMID	0.1	23	GE-SWEST	0.17
8	NO-MID	0.1	24	GE-SOUTH	0.12
9	NO-NORTH1	0.1	25	FINLAND	1.00
10	NO-NORTH2	0.1	26	DK-EAST	0.41
11	NO-NORTH3	0.1	27	DK-WEST	0.59
12	SW-NORTH1	0.17	28	NETHERLANDS	1.00
13	SW-NORTH2	0.17	29	BELGIUM	1.00
14	SW-NORTH3	0.08	30	UK-SOUTH	0.40
15	SW-NORTH4	0.08	31	UK-MID	0.40
16	SW-MID	0.33	32	UK-NORTH	0.20

We assume the battery storage systems have a storage duration of three hours (as in GENeSYS-MOD) and a round-trip efficiency of 88%. The transmission system is modelled as a transport network with linear losses. In the Nordic area, AC lines are assigned a 2% loss and HVDC links 3%, while connections in continental Europe and to offshore wind sites use a 1% loss rate. Because real-world capacity is occasionally reduced by maintenance or unexpected outages, we approximate these effects by assuming a uniform 5% reduction in available capacity on all interconnectors.

5.2 Detailed hydropower

The detailed hydropower data are the same as in the HydroConnect project [9,15–17]. The dataset defines about 1300 hydropower modules for Norway and includes detailed representations of topology, reservoirs, river networks and power plants. Most of these data were originally obtained from the Norwegian Water Resources and Energy Directorate (NVE) [18]. Subsequently, they were augmented with refined production-discharge relationships [19], assumptions about future environmental constraints [20] and about additional small-scale hydropower and refurbished hydropower in Norway by 2050 [15]. Total Norwegian hydropower capacity amounts to 36.1 GW and the average hydropower generation 149.4 TWh yr⁻¹ (baseline assumptions, excluding expansions in the +HydroFlex scenario).

Apart from Norway, the dataset includes detailed descriptions for hydropower topology in Sweden (adopted from ref. [19]). For other countries than Norway and Sweden, hydropower topologies are aggregated representations.

5.3 Electricity demand

Electricity demand assumptions by end-use are derived from the GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials scenario results. In FanSi, total demand is disaggregated into a set of end-use categories, each linked to GENeSYS-MOD variables and assigned specific characteristics. The demand categories considered in FanSi are: Buildings (excluding cooling), cooling, transport (price-responsive), transport (price-inelastic), industry, residual electricity use and lower-voltage grid loss.

For the categories buildings, cooling, price-responsive electric vehicles and industry electricity use, demand is modelled as price-elastic. This is implemented through a mathematical relationship that adjusts electricity consumption in response to deviations from a reference price. For the buildings, cooling, price-responsive electric vehicles categories, an upper price threshold is applied, beyond which demand is curtailed. These thresholds are set at 400 EUR MWh⁻¹ for buildings and cooling and 300 EUR MWh⁻¹ for price-responsive electric vehicles. These thresholds are necessarily stylized, as empirical data on willingness-to-pay for different demand categories is limited. An overview of the demand categories and their main attributes is provided in Table 6.

Table 6. Electricity demand categories defined in FanSi and their key characteristics.

Demand category	Remarks, demand category attributes
Buildings (excl. cooling)	Price-elastic. Temperature-dependent for Norway, Sweden and Denmark. Yearly and weekly time profiles by region adopted from category "Household and services" adopted from HydroCen project [20]. Set equal to 100% of buildings GENeSYS-MOD electricity demand category for Nordic countries and 94% for non-Nordic countries (residual 6% is assumed to be cooling).
Cooling	Price-elastic. Weekly and yearly time profiles reflecting daily and seasonal variations in cooling demand adopted from HydroConnect project [15,21]. Set equal to 6% of buildings GENeSYS-MOD electricity demand category for non-Nordic countries.
Transport (price-responsive)	Price-elastic. Flat yearly time profile. Weekly time profile adopted from category "Electric vehicles" in HydroCen [20]. Set equal to 20% to GENeSYS-MOD transport electricity demand category.
Transport (price-inelastic)	Flat yearly time profile. Weekly time profile adopted from category "Electric vehicles" in HydroCen [20]. Set equal to 80% to GENeSYS-MOD transport electricity demand category.
Industry	Price-elastic. Flat yearly and weekly time profile. Set equal to 100% to GENeSYS-MOD industry electricity demand category.
Residual	Flat yearly and weekly time profile. Set equal to 100% to GENeSYS-MOD residual electricity demand category.
Loss	Assume 2% energy loss in lower-voltage grids and represent this loss as a demand category.

5.4 Energy storage

We implement 3-hourly battery energy storage systems into FanSi based on the GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials scenario results for Li-ion battery energy storage. We assume a battery a round-trip efficiency of 88%. The modelling of batteries is simplified in that it does not consider degradation of Li-ion batteries, maximum or minimum state of charge levels or other operational constraints. Relatively small amounts of compressed air energy storage (CAES) in the NECP Essentials scenario results are merged with Li-ion batteries and treated as Li-ion batteries in the FanSi analysis.

Apart from Norway, for which pumped hydro storage (PHS) is modelled in detail, PHS is represented in simplified manner: Generation from PHS is represented in FanSi as an electricity import option at a relatively high price, and pumping is represented as an electricity export option at a relatively low price. The import/export capacities are set based on GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials scenario results. FanSi will determine endogenously when to import (generate) or export (pump) based on simulated electricity prices.

5.5 Nuclear and thermal power generation

Nuclear and thermal power generation technologies are represented in a stylized manner. For each country, we take total installed capacities for nuclear, biomass, gas, and coal power plants from GENeSYS-MOD and disaggregate them into two generic classes: a low-marginal-cost "base" class and a higher-marginal-cost "flex" (or "peak") class. This stylized split introduces some internal variation within each technology category, allowing part of the capacity to operate at lower price levels while another part is dispatched only during higher-price periods, without attempting to represent detailed unit-level characteristics.

Table 7 summarizes the assumed shares and marginal cost levels for each generic class. Marginal cost assumptions are based on fuel prices and CO₂ prices from NVE [12]⁶, combined with assumed conversion efficiencies and variable operation and maintenance (VOM) costs. The splits between “base” and “flex” classes reflect assumptions rather than empirical estimates.

A further modelling choice concerns coal and gas power capacities in 2050. In the GENeSYS-MOD NECP Essentials scenario, some coal and gas capacities remain installed but exhibit zero generation in 2050. When transferred to FanSi, these capacities may be dispatched endogenously under certain price conditions. To support emissions consistency with the climate ambition underlying the NECP Essentials, these capacities are represented as equipped with carbon capture and storage (CCS) in FanSi, even though they are modelled without CCS in GENeSYS-MOD. This adjustment aims to prevent unrealistically high CO₂ emissions in the FanSi simulations. This affects the costs outlined in Table 7.

Table 7. Overview of the assumed technology splits and marginal cost levels used to represent nuclear and thermal generation in FanSi. VOM = Variable Operation and Maintenance.

Generation technology	Share of total	Marginal cost [EUR MWh ⁻¹]	CO ₂ price [EUR t ⁻¹]	Notes
Nuclear base	75%	0.5	-	Baseload nuclear
Nuclear flex	25%	18	-	Nuclear that will switch off at low prices
Bio base	50%	72	0	Meant to represent relatively low-grade/residual biomass or waste. (20 EUR/MWh fuel) / 30% efficiency + 5 EUR/MWh VOM = 72
Bio flex	50%	155	0	Meant to represent high-value, upgraded biomass (e.g., biomethane) for use in flexible power plants. (60 EUR/MWh fuel) / 40% efficiency + 5 EUR/MWh VOM = 155
Gas base	50%	52	219	(24 EUR/MWh fuel) / 56% efficiency + (0.02 t CO ₂ /MWh * 219 EUR/t) + 5 EUR/MWh VOM = 52
Gas flex	50%	73	219	Assume equal to the marginal cost for Gas base + a markup of 21 EUR/MWh
Coal base	50%	53	219	(9 EUR/MWh fuel) / 33% efficiency + (0.10 t CO ₂ /MWh * 219 EUR/t) + 5 EUR/MWh VOM = 53
Coal flex	50%	74	219	Assume equal to the marginal cost for Gas base + a markup of 21 EUR/MWh

5.6 Wind and solar profiles

Wind and solar generation profiles for 1991–2020 are derived from ERA5 reanalysis data and aggregated from hourly to 3-hourly resolution for use in FanSi [22,23]. Building upon ref. [23], wind time series are rescaled to reproduce the average capacity factors implied by GENeSYS-MOD, ensuring coherence between installed capacities and annual generation across the two modelling frameworks.

⁶ We use NVE’s “base” values for fuel prices and “high” value for CO₂ price, which we consider appropriate given the decarbonization ambition of the NECP Essentials scenario framework.

6 Results: Power price

6.1 Price average

The mean simulated power price is approximately 40 EUR MWh⁻¹ across all areas in Norway in the Base scenario (e.g., 40.1, 42.1 and 42.3 EUR MWh⁻¹ in NO-SOUTH, NO-WESTSOUTH and NO-WESTMID respectively). In contrast, mean prices in the United Kingdom and continental European countries are substantially higher, at around 110 MWh⁻¹ in the Netherlands, 100 EUR MWh⁻¹ across UK areas and 70 EUR MWh⁻¹ across German areas (Figure 6). The relatively low price levels in Norway can likely be explained by the country's positive electricity balance in combination with limited transmission capacity to neighbouring countries. Differences in median prices across regions are considerably smaller than differences in mean prices, reflecting the influence of a limited number of hours with extremely high price in some areas (corresponding to unserved energy events, or "rationing" prices, as represented in the model).

Expansions in transmission capacity in the +TransFlex scenario lead to a reduction in regional price differentials, as illustrated by Figure 6, which presents median power prices for three Norwegian areas in Norway and four non-Norwegian areas as examples.

Figure 6. Median power prices across 30 simulated weather years by scenario for seven selected areas (three areas in Norway and four in other countries).

6.2 Price volatility

Figure 7 provides comparisons of various price volatility indicators. Besides standard deviation and mean daily spread, the figure includes a measure of price volatility calculated in the following way: First, determine the differences between consecutive time steps at the given time resolution (3-hourly, daily or weekly). Next, calculate the standard deviation of these differences. All the indicators displayed in the figure are normalized to the mean price to facilitate comparisons across areas and scenarios.

Focusing on the Norwegian areas shown in Figure 7 and comparing the effects of the four flexibility scenarios in relative terms with the Base scenario as a common reference, we observe that the +HydroFlex and +TimeShiftDemand scenarios have relatively high efficacy in reducing the mean daily spread in Norway. For +HydroFlex, this effect is probably linked to extensive use of hydropower to balance day-night variations associated with the solar cycle in the simulations (see related discussions

in sections 6.4 and 7.2). The +ElasticDemand scenario shows moderate but consistent reductions for all analysed price volatility metrics, both short-term three-hourly and longer-term weekly metrics. +ElasticDemand is the only scenario that exhibits a notable reduction in week-to-week volatility in Norway (“volatility weekly” in Figure 7).

Price volatility increases in the +TransFlex scenario for Norwegian areas, because expanded interconnection exposes Norway more strongly to price variability in neighbouring markets, which exhibit higher volatility in the Base scenario. Conversely, in countries connected to Norway, the +TransFlex scenario tends to reduce price volatility (Figure 7).

Regardless of scenario, price volatility is substantially lower in Norwegian areas than in continental Europe and UK areas. This is the case for all the assessed indicators, but the difference is smaller for the weekly price volatility indicator than for the shorter-term indicators, as Figure 7 illustrates. There is a tendency for the difference in price volatility between Norwegian areas and neighbouring areas to decline in the +TransFlex scenario, but the magnitude of this effect varies by country and indicator. It is important to note that volatility in our simulations is solely driven by weather variability, excluding factors such as variable fuel prices, and market and infrastructure changes.

Figure 7. Indicators of electricity price volatility. All metrics are normalized by the mean price, yielding dimensionless measures. The standard deviation is defined as the price standard deviation divided by the mean price. The mean daily spread corresponds to the mean daily range (daily maximum minus minimum) normalized by the mean price. The three other indicators labelled “volatility” are computed at 3-hourly, daily, and weekly time scales by: (i) calculating successive price changes at the selected temporal resolution; (ii) evaluating the standard deviation of these changes; and (iii) dividing the result by the mean price.

Price duration curves summarize the distribution of electricity prices by ranking all simulated prices from highest to lowest, thereby illustrating the frequency of extreme and moderate price levels. With thirty historical weather years and 2912 three-hourly time steps per year, each scenario produces

87 360 price observations. Figure 8 and Figure 9 display the upper 0-1% of prices in panel (a) and the remaining 1-100% in panel (b) for NO-SOUTH and UK-NORTH, respectively.

All flexibility scenarios except +TransFlex result in increases in floor/low prices compared to the Base scenario in Norwegian areas, exemplified by Figure 8 for the area NO-SOUTH. The results reveal particularly pronounced increases in peak/high prices and decreases in floor/low prices in the +TransFlex scenario compared to the Base scenario in Norwegian areas, particularly NO-SOUTH (Figure 8). These +TransFlex trends are mirrored by changes in continental Europe and the UK in the opposite direction (Figure 9, showing results for UK-NORTH as an example).

Figure 8. Price duration curve for the a) 0-1% and b) 1-100% range of simulated power prices at three-hourly time resolution for the area NO-SOUTH.

Figure 9. Price duration curve for the a) 0-1% and b) 1-100% range of simulated power prices at three-hourly time resolution for the area UK-NORTH.

It is important to note that high-price outcomes are influenced by the assumed curtailment thresholds for price-responsive demand in European countries (Section 5.3). In the present setup, some demand segments are curtailed when prices exceed 300-400 EUR MWh⁻¹. These thresholds should be viewed as indicative of a system under stress as they reflect that some demand is already curtailed at these price levels. A scarcity of prices above these levels does not necessarily imply that the system faces no severe balancing challenges. High-price results should be interpreted with this modelling choice in mind.

6.3 Price across the year

In the Base scenario, average daily prices appear relatively flat across the year, but there appears to be a weak tendency for lower prices in summer. The most pronounced spikes in prices occur in January-April. Figure 10 shows a comparison of daily average prices across the year for the Base and +ElasticDemand scenarios for NO-WESTMID as an example.

Figure 10. Average daily prices across the year for NO-WESTMID for Base and +ElasticDemand scenarios. Solid lines show the median across 30 simulated weather years; dark shaded bands indicate the 25th-75th percentiles, light shaded bands the 5th-95th percentiles, and dashed lines the minimum and maximum values.

6.4 Price across the day

The solar diurnal cycle exerts a strong influence on the 24-hour daily power price variations for most parts of the year (apart from the winter weeks where solar power is at its lowest). Within Norway, this effect is most pronounced in NO-SOUTH due to its particularly strong interconnection with continental Europe. The influence of the solar diurnal cycle on power price in southern Norway is significantly reduced in the +HydroFlex, +ElasticDemand and +TimeShiftDemand scenarios compared to the Base scenario. However, this is not the case for the +TransFlex scenario, which rather shows a change in the opposite direction, with an increased influence of the solar intraday cycle. This result is consistent with the strengthened transmission links between Norway and solar-rich regions under the +TransFlex assumptions.

For nearby regions outside Norway, a weaker but consistent tendency for reduced solar diurnal influence on power price is observed in the +HydroFlex scenario and, to a lesser degree, in the +TimeShiftDemand scenario. For the +TransFlex scenario, the effects are mixed and relatively small in magnitude, with some indications of lower night-time prices but slightly higher mid-day prices, making it difficult to identify a clear direction of change. A possible interpretation is that +TransFlex harmonizes prices across areas (sections 6.1 and 6.2) rather than systematically dampening solar influence. These findings are illustrated by Figure 11 and Figure 12, which present results for NO-SOUTH and UK-MID, respectively.

Figure 11. Median (solid line) and 25th-75th percentile range (shaded area) for 24-hour daily profile for simulated price for NO-SOUTH during the summer months (June-August). The percentiles are calculated across all days in all years. Each subplot compares the Base scenario with one alternative scenario.

Figure 12. Median (solid line) and 25th-75th percentile range (shaded area) for 24-hour daily profile for simulated price for UK-MID during the summer months (June-August). The percentiles are calculated across all days in all years. Each subplot compares the Base scenario with one alternative scenario.

7 Results: Hydropower

This section examines two aspects related to hydropower in Norway: (i) Simulated aggregated reservoir storage over the year, and (ii) intraday patterns of hydropower generation during summer and winter.

7.1 Reservoir storage across the year

The higher assumed capacities in hydropower result in moderately higher reservoir storage levels on average in the +HydroFlex scenario relative to the Base scenario. The minimum and maximum observed levels across the year are only to a small degree affected, however. These results are illustrated in Figure 13, which presents aggregated Norwegian reservoir levels for the Base and +HydroFlex scenarios. Different dynamics are found for the +TransFlex scenario relative to the Base scenario, as the higher assumed capacities in Transmission in +TransFlex result in lower reservoir storage levels on average, and also lower minimum and maximum levels, as illustrated in Figure 14.

In the Base scenario, the minimum simulated reservoir level for Norway is 19%. Across all scenarios, the minimum simulated reservoir level for Norway is 16% (this occurs in early spring in the +TransFlex scenario as shown in Figure 14). By comparison, the lowest reservoir level observed for Norway over the past two decades is 18% [24]. The simulated reservoir levels for Norway in the current results are generally higher than previous FanSi simulations for year 2050 conducted as part of the HydroConnect project [15].

Figure 13. Aggregated Norwegian reservoir levels in the Base and +HydroFlex scenarios. Reservoir levels are expressed as a percentage (%) of total maximum storage capacity. Solid lines show the

median across 30 simulated weather years; dark shaded bands indicate the 25th-75th percentiles, light shaded bands the 5th-95th percentiles, and dashed lines the minimum and maximum values.

Figure 14. Aggregated Norwegian reservoir levels in the Base and +TransFlex scenarios. Reservoir levels are expressed as a percentage (%) of total maximum storage capacity. Solid lines show the median across 30 simulated weather years; dark shaded bands indicate the 25th-75th percentiles, light shaded bands the 5th-95th percentiles, and dashed lines the minimum and maximum values.

Note that the FanSi simulation results for reservoir operation shown in the two previous figures only partially reflect the effects of short-term flexibility. In the stochastic second stage of the FanSi optimization (see Section 2), water values are calculated at weekly resolution, which is too coarse to capture short-term flexibility in reservoir operation. As a result, the full impact on annual storage levels (as shown in the two previous figures) may not be fully represented.

There is significant interannual variation in Norwegian hydropower reservoir management, as is evident from Figure 13 and Figure 14 shown previously. An alternative illustration is provided by Figure 15, which shows aggregated reservoir levels for each individual weather year for Norway for the Base scenario.

Figure 15. Aggregated Norwegian reservoir level for each simulated weather year according to the Base scenario results. Reservoir levels are expressed as a percentage (%) of total maximum storage capacity.

7.2 Hydropower across the day

The 2050 simulations further indicate that hydropower flexibility is extensively used to balance the diurnal variability of solar generation outside the winter season. As shown by the summer profiles in Figure 16, hydropower output closely mirrors the intraday solar cycle. This behaviour highlights a potential role of flexible hydropower in mitigating short-term variability in solar production in the future.

Figure 16. Percentiles for 24-hour daily profiles for simulated hydropower generation during summer (panel a) and winter (panel b) seasons, respectively. The percentiles are calculated across all days in all years. Electricity used for pumping is counted as negative hydropower generation. The results are from the Base scenario and NO-SOUTH area as an example. Summer is taken as June-August, and winter as December-February.

8 Results: Offshore wind power capture price

Differences in price levels and distributions across regions (see Section 6) can result in different revenues for electricity producers. Figure 17 illustrates this by showing mean capture prices for seven offshore wind power areas as an example. By capture price, we mean the ratio of the total revenue from selling electricity to the total electricity sold. As the figure illustrates, capture prices for Norwegian offshore wind power are substantially lower than capture prices for offshore wind power in most other areas. The Norwegian offshore wind capture prices are 43-44% lower than those for the UK and Benelux countries, and around 26% lower than those for Denmark. GE-NORTH is the main exception among the UK and continental European areas, with capture prices comparable to the Norwegian areas. The lower capture prices for GE-NORTH compared to other continental European areas may reflect different factors. It is potentially linked to the relatively high fossil fuel-based power plant capacities still present in Germany (see Section 5.1), to the transmission link between GE-NORTH and NO-SOUTH in Norway, and potentially to other factors.

The lower capture prices in Norway are consistent with generally lower price levels, which in turn reflects Norway's significant net power surplus in Norway and limited interconnection capacity with other Europe, as discussed in Section 6.1. Across the flexibility variants, Norwegian offshore wind capture prices increase moderately in the +HydroFlex, +ElasticDemand and +TransFlex, scenarios. For +HydroFlex and +ElasticDemand, this increase is primarily driven by higher prices during periods of high renewable power output compared to the Base case. By contrast, in the +TransFlex scenario, the increase in capture prices mainly reflects higher overall price levels in Norway, rather than a systematic increase when renewable power output is high.

Under the given assumptions, +TransFlex is the most effective option for reducing cross-regional disparities in capture prices, leading to a more uniform revenues for offshore wind across areas.

Figure 17. Mean capture price across 30 simulated weather years by scenario for seven selected offshore wind farm areas (three areas in Norway and four in other countries).

9 Results: Transmission

The Norway-Europe interconnectors are frequently used for both import and export within same day, as is illustrated by Figure 18 for year 2020 as an example. The observation that cables are used for

both import and export, is also supported by the duration curves for transmission in Figure 19, which shows the power transfer on the NO-SOUTH->GE-NORTH interconnection as an example.

Figure 18. Simulated power transmission across Norway’s HVDC interconnections with other countries for the single year 2020 for the Base scenario plotted at three-hourly resolution.

Figure 19. Power transmission duration curve for the 0-100% range of simulated power transfer at three-hourly time resolution for the interconnection NO-SOUTH->GE-NORTH. Positive value represents export from NO-SOUTH and negative value import to NO-SOUTH.

There is substantial interannual variability in the power exchanges between Norway and other countries. This is illustrated by Figure 20, which shows the weekly means of exchange between NO-SOUTH and GE-NORTH from the Base scenario results.

Figure 20. Weekly means of power exchange from NO-SOUTH to GE-NORTH for each simulated weather year in the Base scenario.

10 Conclusions

By combining a long-term energy system scenario for the year 2050 from GENeSYS-MOD with a detailed stochastic power market representation in FanSi, this case study assesses how different flexibility mechanisms influence operational outcomes in a future Northern European electricity system characterized by high shares of variable renewable energy. We explore four flexibility scenario variants: hydropower flexibility (+HydroFlex), elastic electricity demand (+ElasticDemand), time-shifting of demand (+TimeShiftDemand) and transmission flexibility (+TransFlex). Each flexibility variant is juxtaposed against the Base case to isolate its system-level impacts.

There is substantial intrinsic uncertainty involved in modelling energy systems decades into the future. Uncertainty also arises from assumptions needed when integrating scenario results from GENeSYS-MOD into FanSi, and from the simplified representations of different forms of flexibility in our FanSi analysis. As was noted in Section 4, the flexibility scenarios (except partly +HydroFlex) are highly stylized and designed to support relative rather than absolute assessments of flexibility options. It is also important to emphasize that the FanSi results capture operational effects only and do not account for investment costs, which should be considered when interpreting the findings.

Despite these uncertainties and modelling simplifications, the analysis sheds light on the system-level roles and mechanisms of hydropower flexibility, demand-side flexibility and transmission expansion, and reveals how each can shape price formation, hydropower operation and system dynamics in a high-renewables future scenario for Europe.

The main findings and messages from the analysis are as follows.

- Norway's substantial net power surplus, mainly due to large wind capacities, leads to pronounced disparities in both average prices and price volatility between Norwegian areas and continental Europe and the UK areas. Such price differences can have distributional consequences, including for producer revenues, as illustrated by the offshore wind capture price results.
- These cross-regional differences in price levels and volatility are reduced in the +TransFlex scenario relative to the Base case, but only moderately. This suggests that very large expansions of cross-border interconnection would be required to achieve broadly uniform price levels and volatility across regions.
- Episodes of very high prices occur in several countries, including the United Kingdom (Figure 9), indicating a potential lack of flexibility under the NECP Essentials framework when assessed in FanSi's stochastic multi-year setting. High-price outcomes should be interpreted with caution given the substantial uncertainties involved, especially the stylized curtailment thresholds for price-responsive demand (Section 5.3) and the representation of remaining coal capacities in the year 2050 (Section 5.1).
- Intraday variability driven by the solar day-night cycle exerts a strong influence on both power prices and Norwegian hydropower operation during most of the year (outside the winter season). Within Norway, this effect is most pronounced in the southernmost area (NO-SOUTH) due to its particularly strong interconnection with continental Europe.
- There is substantial interannual variation in prices, Norwegian reservoir levels, cross-border flows and other system indicators across individual weather years, underscoring the potential importance of multi-year stochastic analysis.
- Despite Norway's substantial net power surplus on an average annual level, Norway-Europe interconnections are largely bidirectional, often used for both import and export within the same day.
- All flexibility scenarios except +TransFlex reduce price volatility in Norway relative to the Base case. In contrast, price volatility in Norway increases under +TransFlex because stronger interconnection exposes Norwegian prices more directly to higher volatility in neighbouring markets. As we have already noted in Section 6.2, weather variability is the sole driver of volatility in our simulations. We only quantify price volatility only over timescales up to one week.
- +HydroFlex and +TimeShiftDemand appear particularly effective at mitigating short-term variability associated with the solar day-night cycle. This is reflected in significant reductions in mean daily price spreads and a weakened influence of solar generation on summer price formation, but more limited effects on day-to-day and week-to-week volatility.

- +ElasticDemand exhibits comparatively weaker impacts on intraday price spreads, but stronger reductions in day-to-day and week-to-week price volatility, indicating a greater relevance for managing stochastic variability associated with wind power. These interpretations could be further tested through analysis of individual low-wind and high-wind periods, which lies beyond the scope of the present study.
- +TransFlex primarily reduces regional differences, both differences in average price levels and in price volatility. As such, transmission expansion complements, rather than substitutes for, temporal flexibility options such as hydropower flexibility and demand-side response.

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